

Mixed Ligand Complex Formation of Nickel(II) with 2,2'-Bipyridylamine and Thio Acid

J. D. JOSHI*

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120

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Potentiometric studies on mixed ligand complex formation of Ni^{II} with 2,2'-bipyridylamine (A) and thio acids (L) have been carried out at 25, 35 and 45°, where L = thioglycolic acid (TGA), thiolactic acid (TLA) and thiomalic acid (TMA). Stability constant and associated parameters have been discussed. Some solid complexes have been isolated. All the complexes showed antimicrobial effect.

The present work reports the results of the study of equilibrium constants of heterochelates of Ni^{II} with 2,2'-bipyridylamine, amino and thio acids in aqueous media. The complexes have been characterised using ir, ¹H nmr, magnetic, conductance and elemental analysis data. Their antimicrobial activity has also been studied.

Results and Discussion

Studies on ternary complexes containing Ni^{II}-2,2'-bipyridylamine as the primary ligand (A) have shown¹⁻³ that in the presence of an aromatic nitrogen donor metal ion becomes more selective and discriminating to the donor groups on the incoming secondary ligand. [(Ni.A)]²⁺ binds secondary ligand with anionic oxygen donors O⁻-O⁻ much more firmly than ligands with neutral nitrogen donors N-N. The affinity for

ligands with S and O donors lies between that observed for pure O⁻-O⁻ and N-N ligands. The behaviour of 2,2'-bipyridylamine is similar to that of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline^{4,5}

The values of ternary formation constant are in the order : Ni.A.TGA < Ni.A.TLA < Ni.A.TMA. This order can be explained in terms of their structures and basicities⁶. It is found that $\Delta \log K$ values are negative for the pairs TGA-glycine, TLA- α -alanine and aspartic acid⁴. Thus behaviour of thio acids in the ternary system is same as that of σ -bonding^{1,7} ligands like amino acids and dihydroxy aromatic compounds. The decrease in formation constants with increase of temperature (Table 1) indicates complex formation reactions being exothermic.

TABLE I-MIXED LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS* OF Ni.A.L COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp: = 25, 35 and 45° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$), Ionic strength (μ) = 0.2 M (NaClO₄)

L**	25°				35°	45°
	log $K_{Ni.L}^{Ni}$	log $K_{Ni.L_2}^{Ni.L}$	log $K_{Ni.A.L}^{Ni.A}$	$\Delta \log K$	log $K_{Ni.A.L}^{Ni.A}$	log $K_{Ni.A.L}^{Ni.A}$
TGA	6.78	6.63	6.59	-0.19	6.36	6.08
TLA	7.31	6.98	6.78	-0.53	6.45	6.21
TMA	7.62	6.62	7.99	0.37	6.95	6.22
Glycine	5.90	5.05	5.48	-0.42	5.04	5.30
α -Alaine	5.55	4.53	5.28	-0.27	5.17	5.10
L-Aspartic acid	7.12	5.32	6.75	-0.37	6.41	6.18

* Accuracy = ± 0.05 units; $\Delta \log K = \log K_{Ni.A.L}^{Ni.A} - \log K_{Ni.L}^{Ni}$. **L = 2,2'-bipyridylamine.

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, North Gujarat University, Patan-384 265.

Solid thio complexes : The elemental analysis data (Table 2) of the complexes⁸ corresponds to 1 : 1 : 1 composition. Their electroneutral nature is indicated by lower molar conductivity. Thermogravimetric analysis of all the complexes show loss in weight corresponding to one water molecule in the range 83–100°. It indicates that one water molecule is present as water of crystallisation. Decomposition of all the complexes starts above 300°. All the complexes are paramagnetic corresponding to two unpaired electrons. It may be due to solvent molecules in the fifth and sixth position of the square-planar Ni^{II} complex resulting in distorted octahedral shape⁹.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF Ni.A.L. HETEROCHELATES

Compd.	Analytical %: Found/(Caled.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
	Metal	N	S	
[NiA.TGA].H ₂ O	17.20 (17.26)	12.28 12.35	9.45 9.46	2.97
[NiA.TLA].H ₂ O	16.50 (16.58)	11.89 11.86	9.02 9.04	3.06
[NiA.TMA].H ₂ O	14.83 (14.75)	10.53 10.55	8.00 8.04	3.10

^aA = 2,2'-bipyridylamine.

Ir spectra indicate the presence of 2,2'-bipyridylamine and thio acid in the complexes. The broad band at 3 450 cm⁻¹ (hydrogen bonded OH) indicates presence of water molecule in the structure. The bands at 3 080 and 2 900 cm⁻¹ correspond to aromatic and aliphatic C-H stretching frequencies. The band expected at 2 550 cm⁻¹ (S-H) is absent in all the complexes indicating that hydrogen atom of S-H group gets dissociated as a result of coordination of sulphur with Ni^{II}.

¹H nmr spectra of Ni-2,2'-bipyridylamine-TGA complex reveal that unpaired electron greatly influences the signals. Considering appropriate valence bond structures it can be found that there will be positive spin density on 2 and 4 carbon atoms and spin correlation will produce a negative spin density at 1, 3 and 5 carbon atoms. Since the spin density at the proton is antiparallel to that on carbon, hydrogen at 1 and 6

4 are expected to be shielded while 1, 3 and 5 protons are deshielded. Similarly, the hydrogen of water will be deshielded. The three signals which appear at the low field may be assigned these deshielded protons. Tentatively the signals around 5030 Hz may be attributed to water molecule protons while the 1 (5) and 3 protons are assigned the signals around 2030 and 3000 Hz respectively.

The ligands and metal chelates were studied for their antimicrobial behaviour towards pseudomonas. The ligands showed good growth of pseudomonas and its metal chelate of Ni^{II} showed significant inhibition of growth of the test organisms.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade and all the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The proton-ligand and ternary metal-ligand formation constants were determined in aqueous media at ionic strength 0.2 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄) and 25, 35 and 45° using modified Irving-Rossotti titration technique¹⁰. A 1 : 1 : 1 ratio of M : A : L was used for the equilibrium study. The titrations were carried out under an atmosphere of nitrogen in a thermostatic bath ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

The pH measurements were carried out with an Elico LI 10T pH meter. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out using a Mettler M-3 balance attached with a microprocessor TA-3000 system at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ in air. ¹H nmr spectra were on a Bruker 400 instrument.

The ternary thio complexes were synthesised from aqueous solution of nickel nitrate. A mixture of nickel nitrate (0.5 mol; 10 ml) and 2,2'-bipyridylamine (0.5 mol; 8.0 ml) was stirred well and to it TGA, TLA or TMA (0.5 mol; 10 ml) was added. pH of the mixture was then raised to ~7.0, ~6.0 and ~5.0 respectively, using NaOH (0.5 mol). The resulting solids were washed with water and alcohol, and dried.

The antimicrobial activity was tested with the usual procedure.

The stability constants of the ternary complexes were calculated by normal pH-metric technique^{1,2}. It

is presumed that 1 : 1 [Ni(A)]²⁺ complex is completely formed³ before the coordination of the secondary ligand. Ni.A.L. is stable upto pH ~7.5.

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